

Analyzing Randomness in Point Patterns: An Algorithmic Approach

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Abstract

There are multiple methods available to determine if a set of points is distributed randomly, clustered, or dispersed. These methods usually involve comparing the expected distances between points to the actual distances, assuming no barriers are present. However, what qualifies as a "random" distribution can be affected by various socio-environmental factors like wetlands or transportation networks. This tool introduces a series of spatial analysis steps and statistical tests to explore the relationship between observed point patterns and potential spatial drivers (e.g., polygons). If any of these drivers influence the point distribution, the assumption of randomness must be reevaluated. The algorithm is implemented in Python as a QGIS script, with two primary phases: the first deals with overlay operations and preliminary calculations, and the second applies a chi-square goodness-of-fit test with Bonferroni correction..

1.0 Introduction

Spatial statistics, a key area in several research fields, has advanced considerably, especially in relation to point distribution patterns. For example, studies on population distribution patterns in ecological systems have used complex null models to identify influencing factors. One such study explored the randomness of spatial patterns through Poisson processes, revealing how habitat variability and dispersal limitations shape dominant species' distributions. These findings deepen our understanding of ecosystem dynamics.

New statistical measures, such as the level of heterogeneity (LH*) and normalized LH* (NLH*), provide valuable insights into deviations from complete randomness. Researchers have confirmed these measures' robustness through simulation and empirical validation. Additionally, Ripley's K function and correlation functions have been employed to understand species distribution in ecological systems, showing that species tend to aggregate, though this tendency weakens with increased scale, moving toward a random distribution. Key factors influencing these patterns include habitat diversity and dispersal constraints.

Further work includes fractal dimension analysis, introducing a new statistical test based on fractal dimensionality, which offers an alternative to traditional spatial analysis methods. Researchers have also explored the effects of spatial randomness in inference processes, especially regarding spatial autocorrelation measures like Moran's I. These studies emphasize the complex dynamics of spatial patterns in various contexts, including social media and mobile object trajectories.

Despite these advancements, most existing methods for analyzing spatial distribution patterns do not account for barriers. Factors such as socio-environmental influences and infrastructure can shape point distributions. This tool incorporates spatial analysis techniques and statistical tests to examine the relationship between point patterns and spatial drivers, implemented as a Python-based QGIS plugin. The process includes overlay operations and preliminary calculations, followed by a chi-square goodness-of-fit test. If any drivers affect the pattern, the assumption of randomness must be reconsidered.

2.0 Method Details

This method operates on the premise that space is non-homogeneous and contains barriers that influence spatial patterns, such as soil types or land use. Before confirming the randomness of a pattern, the potential impact of drivers must be assessed. If no drivers are found to influence the pattern, other tests, such as the Average Nearest Neighbor (ANN) and Ripley's K, can be applied to classify the pattern. If a spatial dependence is identified, the Randomness Point Pattern Test (RPPT) is introduced.

The process involves two main steps (Figure 1). The first addresses overlay processes and basic calculations, while the second applies the chi-square goodness-of-fit test. The method uses two Python scripts integrated into the QGIS platform. The plugin offers various functionalities using the QGIS Python API, including an interface for defining point data layers, selecting study areas, and choosing driver layers.

Figure 1. Method flowchart.

2.1 Overlay Process and Data Preparation

Users first define the point data layer to be analyzed and select a method for delimiting the study area. Options include the Concave Hull or Minimum Bounding Geometry algorithms, which generate areas around the points for further analysis. A buffer is then applied to extend the study area, and the driver layer is clipped based on the buffer. The polygon data is aggregated by the field of interest, and points within each geometry are counted. The data is normalized to calculate the expected number of points, assuming a random distribution.

2.1.1 Defining the Boundaries Around the Points to be Used as The Study Area: As the first step, the user needs to define the point data layer to be analyzed, select the area delimitation algorithm, and define the layer with the driver data (Figure 2).
`processing.run('native:concavehull')` or `processing.run('native:minimumboundinggeometry')`

Users can choose Concave Hull or Minimum Bounding Geometry methods in this step. The Concave Hull method is used to create an adjustable area around the points, as illustrated in figure 1. Users can set values between 0 and 1, where 0 represents the tightest fit around the points, and 1 corresponds to a convex hull. On the other hand, Minimum Bounding Geometry is a native algorithm that offers four types of procedures: 'Envelope (bounding box)', 'Minimal Oriented Rectangle', 'Minimal Enclosing Circle', and 'Concave Hull'. It is important to note, however, that although listed, Concave Hull has not been included as a configurable option in the Minimum Bounding Geometry procedure (the default adjustment value is set to 1 and cannot be changed).

Figure 2. Method Part 1.

2.1.2 Expand The Study Area. Buffering (Influence Area):
`processing.run('native:buffer')`

A buffer is created with a user-defined distance in meters (default is 1000 meters) based on the study area polygon created in the previous step.

2.1.3 Clip the Drive Layer with the Final Study Area. Clip Interested Area:
`processing.run('native:clip')`

This is an overlay process in which the polygon layer (the drive) is cut by the buffer area that was previously defined.

2.1.4 Aggregate the Polygon Data by Field of Interest:
`processing.run('native:aggregate')`

Aggregates the geometries in the area of interest into a single entity with a shared value for the classification field of the polygon. The field must be a text data type. This step aggregates the geometries in the area of interest into a multipolygon with a unique attribute. The aggregation process reduces the number of objects in the analysis by combining several geometries that share the same attribute value into a single register. This facilitates analysis by reducing the complexity of the data.

2.1.5 Count Points in Each Attribute Geometry:
`processing.run('native:countpointsinpolygon')`

Counts points within each aggregated geometry. After aggregation, it is necessary to count points within each attribute geometry. This step calculates the number of event layer points in each drive layer geometry. This quantity is the observed number of events per class.

2.1.16 Normalize and Calculate Data:
`processing.run('native:fieldcalculator')`

Calculate the ratio of each class's area to the layer's total area. This ratio is then applied to the total number of points, resulting in a field with the expected number of points in the class. If the distribution of events were random and therefore homogeneous in all classes, the expected and observed number of points should be close. The script output is a Calculated drive layer with the observed and expected number of points as attributes.

2.2 Chi-square Goodness-of-fit Test

The second phase (Figure 3) applies the chi-square goodness-of-fit test, including normalization of the data and a Bonferroni correction to adjust significance levels. This method helps identify whether the observed distribution of points differs significantly from what would be expected under a random distribution.

Figure 3. Method Part 2.

The Bonferroni correction (BC) is a widely used method to address the issue of multiple comparisons in statistical hypothesis testing. When multiple statistical tests are performed simultaneously or within the same dataset, the likelihood of obtaining at least one significant result merely by chance increases. This increased risk of Type I errors (i.e., false positives) can lead to overstated overall error rates and undermine the reliability of the findings.

BC adjusts the significance threshold for individual tests to account for the increased risk of false positives due to multiple comparisons. It does so by dividing the desired overall significance level (usually denoted as α and typically set at 0.05) by the number of comparisons being made. This adjusted significance level is further used as the new threshold for determining statistical significance in each individual test. Thus, if there are m tests being conducted, the Bonferroni corrected significance level $\alpha_{Bonferroni}$ is calculated as:

$$\alpha_{Bonferroni} = \frac{\alpha}{m} \quad (1)$$

Where α is the desired overall significance level (e.g., 0.05) and m is the number of comparisons being made. For each individual test, the null hypothesis is rejected if the p-value associated with the test is less than or equal to $\alpha_{Bonferroni}$.

By using the Bonferroni correction, we aim to control the familywise error rate (FWER), which is the probability of making at least one Type I error across all the tests being conducted. While the Bonferroni correction is effective at controlling the FWER, it can be conservative, especially when the number of comparisons is large. In such cases, other methods like the Šidák correction or false discovery rate (FDR) control may be considered as alternatives.

Nevertheless, the Bonferroni correction is a straightforward and widely used method for mitigating the problem of multiple comparisons and maintaining the integrity of statistical hypothesis testing in research.

This step highlights specific attributes influencing point patterns, moving beyond the null hypothesis of expected values equaling observed values. The input of this script is the Calculated drive layer created in the previous script. The output is a text report of the evaluation.

3.0 Conclusions

This innovative method and implementation are extremely valuable for spatial analysis and interpretation of point patterns. Its two-step process allows users to incorporate external data and use it in various scenarios with polygonal boundaries, such as hypsometric classes, soil classes, and many more. In addition, linear drives such as power transmission lines or transport networks can be evaluated using feature buffers.

It should be noted that the use of very tight cuts around the points (concave hull with values close to zero) reduces the area where the occurrence of the phenomenon is not observed, and consequently, the number of expected points for these areas. This decision can result in the acceptance of H_0 (expected values = observed values), since it predominantly computes areas of occurrence. The acceptance of H_0 may also result from the level of knowledge about the point pattern phenomenon and/or zonal

(layer driver: polygons) due to the absence of data or the use of data with different levels of detail.

The scripts developed to analyze spatial randomness (Random Point Process) are easily accessible within QGIS and can be adapted or modified using Python and various packages. This makes it user-friendly, even for those with limited programming experience. The script runs in about 30 seconds and is optimized for systems with up to 16GB of RAM. The user interface includes extensive help documentation. Results are presented descriptively, including interpretations based on p-value, critical values and Bonferroni correction. Using native QGIS functions such as 'native: Concavehull' results in smoother processing and allows broad usage across different versions of QGIS.

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